

Beyond the Standard Model: A Framework for Structural Models and Mass Calculation Methods of Fundamental Particles and Their Broader Extensions

Han-Song Tian(田寒松)*

keywords: models beyond the Standard Model, matter-charge hypothesis, quark mass calculation, the calculation method for particle mass, the calculation method for particle spin magnetic moment, the calculation method for particle radius

PACS: 12.60.-i, 12.10.-g, 12.15.Ff, 04.50.+h

ABSTRACT

The Standard Model of particle physics, the core framework of modern physics, has achieved significant accomplishments in many areas but also faces several challenges. For example, the Higgs mechanism explains the origin of the mass of fundamental particles, but it lacks a mechanism for calculating these masses and fails to explain their diversity. Fundamental particles, the primary subjects of research within the Standard Model, are viewed as indivisible point particles without internal structure. However, this study considers them as dynamic orbital structures formed from a more basic substance—termed “matter-charges.” It suggests that all particles are stable structures composed of varying numbers of matter-charges. In this framework, a particle’s structure—and thereby its mass—is determined by the number of matter-charges composing it. Thus, with the structures of fundamental particles such as electrons, muons, taus, quarks, and Higgs particles determined, their masses can also be accurately calculated, presenting significant differences from the Higgs mechanism. Furthermore, this framework illustrates the complete process from the formation to the stabilization of particles, and provides a consistent method for directly calculating the mass, radius, and magnetic moment of hadrons, which significantly differs from the Standard Model. The article delineates the structures of dozens of particles, computing their properties that closely align with experimental data, thereby demonstrating the reliability of the method. Moreover, as the foundational understanding shifts from fundamental particles to matter-charges, this framework’s impact extends beyond the domain of particle physics. Further details are available in the supplementary information.

INTRODUCTION

The Standard Model currently stands as the premier theory in particle physics, covering fundamental particles and their interactions^{1,2,3}. It has effectively accounted for the properties and interactions of particles, with the notable exception of gravity.

This research presents an alternative framework, conceptualizing particles as stable orbital structures constituted by a foundational substance known as “matter-charge.” The orbital structures thus formed are referred to as “toroidal-orbits.” In this framework, the toroidal-orbit structure of particles and their properties, such as mass, radius, and magnetic moment, form an integrated whole. Moreover, it provides a unified interpretation of the four fundamental forces

* tianxuejian2017@163.com

—including gravity—and bridges relativity with quantum mechanics.

This framework could have been regarded as an vital complement to the Standard Model. While the Standard Model’s Higgs mechanism accounts for the mass of fundamental particles, it does not adequately explain the diversity of these masses.

In the framework, different particles are constituted by distinct toroidal-orbit structures, thereby possessing varying quantities of matter-charge. While the quantity of matter-charge directly correlates with the particle’s mass, allowing for straightforward descriptions and calculations of the masses for these varied structures, including fundamental particles. The paper presents formulas for the masses of electrons, muons, tau particles, quarks, and Higgs bosons, with calculated values closely matching measured values.

However, the shift in our fundamental understanding of matter—from the Standard Model’s fundamental particles to the matter-charge in the new framework—creates significant differences between the two models’ perceptions.

Firstly, in the Standard Model, fundamental particles are considered point particles without internal structure, whereas only hadrons (e.g., protons, neutrons, believed to be composed of quarks bound by the strong force) possess a measurable radius, aligning with observations in high-energy physics experiments. In the new framework, however, both fundamental particles and hadrons share similar structures, allowing their radii to be calculated using the same method. We have calculated the radii of particles such as protons, neutrons, and π mesons, with results fully consistent with measured values. While the radii of fundamental particles can also be calculated, specific mechanisms render this attribute unmeasurable experimentally, yet it can be validated through subsequent calculations.

Second, in the Standard Model, the structure and properties of hadrons are described by Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD)^{4,5}. However, the strong cou-

pling between quarks makes precise mass calculations for hadrons theoretically possible but practically complex. In the new framework, as there is no fundamental difference between the structures of hadrons and fundamental particles, the same method can be applied to calculate the mass of hadrons. Calculating particle mass in the new model is straightforward, allowing us to provide numerous mass calculation formulas due to the repetitive application of the same method. Therefore, the main text presents examples of a few typical particles, with additional calculations detailed in the Supplementary Information(SI).

Third, in the Standard Model, the magnetic moments of leptons are calculated using Quantum Electrodynamics (QED), while those of hadrons are computed through QCD. In contrast, the new framework attributes magnetic moments to the orbital motion of matter-charge, enabling a unified calculation method for all particles, irrespective of their classification as leptons or hadrons.

Fourth, the Standard Model considers fundamental particles as the most elementary constituents of matter, using gauge bosons (such as photons, gluons, and $W&Z$ bosons) to explain fundamental interactions. In the new framework, these gauge bosons are interpreted as structures formed by matter-charge, inevitably leading to a shift in our understanding of fundamental forces. This allows us to approach electromagnetic interactions from a more fundamental perspective, and thus, enables the incorporation of gravity into a unified framework.

Fifth, the new particle structure directly derives relativistic effects, and quantum mechanics is reinterpreted within this framework, allowing both to be encompassed by a single unified theory.

The aforementioned points are crucial but challenging to convey within a single paper. Hence, the main text focuses on the new framework and particle structures, the formation and stabilization mechanisms of particles, and the calculation methods for mass, radius, and magnetic moment, presenting for-

mulas and results. For more detailed information, see the series of papers in the SI.

Having highlighted the foundational differences and potential theoretical synergies between our model and the Standard Model, we now turn to a detailed exposition of the underpinnings of our approach.

THE MATTER-CHARGE HYPOTHESIS

The pivotal distinction between the new framework and previous understandings lies in the perception of the most fundamental substance. In the “matter-charge hypothesis”, all particles, including fundamental ones, are considered as toroidal-orbits composed of matter-charge, forming various stable structures. Thus, all physical concepts related to tangible matter originate from matter-charge. Crucially, abstract physical concepts such as charge, energy, and mass are also intimately connected to matter-charge.

Matter-charges are categorized into two types, reflecting charge’s fundamental duality. As previously mentioned, within this innovative framework, the core of electromagnetic interactions is identified as the direct interplay among matter-charges, whereby the quantity of a singular type of matter-charge directly determines the magnitude of the electric charge. Concurrently, when positive and negative matter-charges coexist in equal measure within a structure, their total quantity is manifested as the structure’s energy. It will later be shown that particles are spatial structures formed by equal amounts of both types of matter-charges. Consequently, the energy expressed by the structure is inherently the quantity of matter-charges composing the particle, thereby directly linking the concepts of energy and tangible matter. Similarly, this concept suggests that energy transfer involves the simultaneous redistribution of positive and negative matter-charges.

Building on the aforementioned insights, our framework introduces a comprehensive perspective on the omnipresence of matter-charges within the spa-

tial continuum, spotlighting the pivotal role played by background matter-charges. These matter-charges underpin the expansive milieu that enables the existence and manifestation of all material constructs and physical phenomena.

In fact, matter-charges in space play a central role in the majority of physical phenomena. However, for the purposes of this paper, examining a particle’s toroidal-orbit structure suffices for precise calculations of particle properties. Thus, more in-depth content related to space matter-charges will be elaborated in the SI.

Building on the foundational mass-energy equivalence, an unequivocal correlation is established between energy and mass. Within the ambit of the proposed framework, which positions matter-charge as a pivotal intermediary, an interconvertibility between energy and charge is facilitated. Therefore, whether it concerns mass, energy, or electric charge, all can be described by the quantity of matter-charge. Particles, viewed as tangible matter, are spatial structures formed by matter-charge, and the space surrounding these particles is also permeated with matter-charge. This forms the fundamental condition for interactions between particles and space. Thus, the sole concept of matter-charge suffices to describe all phenomena within the universe, embodying the essence of the matter-charge hypothesis.

PARTICLE TOROIDAL-ORBIT MODEL

Based on the matter-charge hypothesis, the “particle toroidal-orbit model” reimagines particles as dynamic structures of matter-charges in toroidal-orbits. This model provides a unified explanation for particle properties, including mass, charge, radius and magnetic moments, and provides a coherent framework that, when validated against experimental data, calculates these properties with unprecedented precision.

In the theoretical framework introduced here, particles are envisioned as dynamic, stable enti-

ties consisting of hierarchical toroidal-orbits, with each toroidal-orbit constituted by self-equilibrating matter-charges. The primary geometric characteristics of these toroidal-orbits, specifically their radius and width (or cross-sectional diameter), are directly linked to the number of matter-charges that comprise them. Experimentally measured electromagnetic radii of particles effectively reflect the dimensions of the outermost toroidal-orbit. The mass of a particle corresponds to the energy stored across all hierarchical toroidal-orbits, precisely the number of equal amounts of positive and negative matter-charges. Interestingly, although the electric fields generated by these equal amounts of positive and negative matter-charges neutralize each other, only revealing the particle's net charge, their rotational actions across different toroidal levels elicit diverse magnetic fields. These magnetic fields, rather than completely cancelling out, combine to form the particle's magnetic moment. Importantly, it is the matter-charges associated with the particle's mass, rather than its net charge, that are the primary contributors to the magnetic moment.

Particle Initial Toroidal-Orbits

In the Standard Model, particles are categorized based on their fundamental properties and types of interactions. Quarks play a central role. However, under the new framework, the fact that each particle exhibits distinct attribute values suggests that each possesses a unique toroidal-orbit structure. Although the masses of these particles may seem unpatterned, they can actually be derived in a unified manner. Moreover, despite the existence of several hundred known particles, their formation is based on surprisingly simple principles. Quarks can also be described by this framework.

In our model, a unit charge corresponds to a specific number of single-type matter-charges. Based on this specific quantity and the interactions between matter-charges, two special stable toroidal-orbits are

derived, each corresponding to a specific quantity of matter-charges, thereby embodying specific amounts of energy. These standard modules for constructing all particles are named r_{-137} and r_{-861} . Their energy capacities, E_{-137} and E_{-861} , correspond to 137 times and 861 times the rest energy of an electron, respectively, with 137 being the reciprocal of $\alpha = 1/137.035999206(11)^6$ and 861 being its product with 2π .

Particles are formed through a process that starts with initial basic toroidal-orbit combinations and evolves into their final, stable structures. The matter-charges that make up the final structure of particles all originate from each particle's initial toroidal-orbits. In Table 1, we list the initial basic toroidal-orbit combinations for some commonly studied particles as examples.

Table 1 | Initial Toroidal-Orbit Configurations for Selected Particles.

Name	Type	r_{-861}	r_{-137}
Muon (μ)	Lepton	1	0
Tau (τ)	Lepton	4	1
Proton (p)	Baryon	2	1
Λ	Baryon	0	16
Ξ	Baryon	3	1
Pion (π)	Meson	0	2
η	Meson	1	2
η'	Meson	2	2
$B^\pm$	Meson	12	0
B_S^0	Meson	12	2
$B_C^\pm$	Meson	14	2
J/ψ	Meson	6	7
χ_{c0}	Meson	8	0

The initial toroidal-orbits of additional particles are described in the SI. In fact, determining the initial toroidal-orbits for the majority of particles, including those not listed in the SI, is straightforward. It requires satisfying two conditions: the total energy of the initial toroidal-orbit slightly exceeds the actual

mass of the particle, and it must allow for the formation of the described stable particle structures.

Particle Stability Structures and Mass Calculations

The initial toroidal-orbits provide the matter-charges required for particle formation. However, for a particle structure to satisfy specific stability conditions, its constituent matter-charges must undergo reorganization. We briefly illustrate this process using one of the most fundamental particles—the proton—as an example.

While the Standard Model considers quarks as constituents of composite particles, in our new model, the proton is an independent toroidal-orbit structure, initially comprising two r_{-861} and one r_{-137} orbits. This corresponds to a specific initial energy value, $E_{p0} = E_{-861} \times 2 + E_{-137} = E_e \times (4\pi + 1)/\alpha = E_e \times 1859.08$, slightly greater than the proton's actual mass E_p , which is about $E_e \times 1836.15$. The matter-charges are then evenly divided into four parts, recombined into pairs, and arranged in a perpendicular, interlocking structure as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The toroidal-orbit structure of a proton.

Therefore, the energy capacity of each toroidal-orbit of the proton should be $E_{p0} \times \frac{1}{4}$, but the actual energy is $E_p \times \frac{1}{4}$. This indicates that there is an energy gap in the toroidal-orbits of the proton.

As shown in Figure 1, this energy gap also corresponds to the intersections of toroidal-orbits, and as will be discussed later, the physical properties exhibited by the intersections of toroidal-orbits are identical to the physical quantities of quarks. In fact, the

quarks in the Standard Model are merely the intersections of toroidal-orbits in the particle toroidal-orbit model.

The perpendicular interlocking of these toroidal-orbits creates a shielding effect, with the shielded section's length equating to the width of the other toroidal-orbit, also corresponding to the energy gap in the toroidal-orbits. Once the capacity of the toroidal-orbits is established, their geometric characteristics such as radius, circumference, and width can be determined by formulas. In the proton's toroidal-orbits, the length of the energy gap is given by $C_p \times \frac{E_{p0} \times \frac{1}{4} - E_p \times \frac{1}{4}}{E_{p0} \times \frac{1}{4}}$.

The length of energy gap on the toroidal-orbits is placed on the left side of the equation, and the formula for the nested toroidal-orbit's width is placed on the right side. When these two values match, we obtain the structural formula of the particle. This reflects a set of tightly nested toroidal-orbits, which is the condition for the particle's stability. This formula conveys the structural information of the particle, allowing us to calculate its mass. For instance, the structural formula for the proton is presented as:

$$\frac{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times \frac{1}{4} - \frac{E_p}{E_e} \times \frac{1}{4}}{\left(\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times \frac{1}{4}\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times \frac{1}{4}}}$$

By substituting the electron rest energy, $E_e = 0.51099895000(15)$ MeV⁷, into the formula, the calculated rest energy of the proton, E_p , is determined to be 938.095 MeV. This value is close to the proton's actual measured mass, $E_p = 938.27208816(29)$ MeV⁷, indicating a small discrepancy.

By linking the length of the energy gap on the toroidal-orbit with the width of the nested toroidal-orbit, we can calculate the mass of the particle. Conversely, by inputting the mass of the particle and some known information, we can also determine the length of the energy gap on the toroidal-orbit and the width of the nested toroidal-orbit, thereby verifying the particle's stability. For example, the proton's energy gap length on its toroidal-orbit is 6.53645×10^{-17} m, closely matching the toroidal-orbit width of 6.43940×10^{-17} m,

with a minute difference of only $9.7 \times 10^{-19} \text{m}$. The two sets of toroidal-orbits tightly nest within each other, contributing to the proton's high stability.

In the structure of protons, comprising four toroidal-orbits, all matter-charges originate from their own initial toroidal-orbits. For most other particles, matter-charges from initial toroidal-orbits generally reorganize into a single toroidal-orbit, which then interlocks with either r_{-137} or r_{-861} , or with their associated stable toroidal-orbits, with the constituent matter-charges derived from space. This also represents the practical application of matter-charges in space within particle physics, where they help particles form stable orbital structures.

Thus, although these particles also form stable configurations with interlocking toroidal-orbits where the energy gap length matches another toroidal-orbit's width, their stability is not as robust as that of the proton. Nevertheless, for researchers, calculating the energy gap length on these particle toroidal-orbits and determining their final structures, or calculating their masses, becomes a procedural task. Only a few particles possess unique structures that require individual analysis.

Structural Formulas of More Particles

Muons, tau leptons, and all hadrons exhibit similar nested toroidal-orbit structures, thus they can be described or their masses can be calculated using a similar methodology. The detailed derivation can be found in the SI; here we present a preliminary display.

For example, the structural formula for the π^0 meson is outlined as:

$$\frac{\frac{2}{\alpha} - \frac{E_{\pi^0}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} - \frac{E_{\pi^0}}{E_e}\right)^2} = \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}}}\right) \times \sqrt{2}.$$

The left side of the formula corresponds to the length of the energy gap in the π^0 meson toroidal-orbit, while the terms within the brackets on the right side represent the formula for the width of the

toroidal-orbit, corresponding to the width of r_{-861} . The details are discussed in the Methods section. The factor of $\sqrt{2}$ on the right side of the formula indicates that the two sets of toroidal-orbits within the particle are not interlocked perpendicularly but are inclined at a 45° angle, making the length of the energy gap $\sqrt{2}$ times the width of the interlocking toroidal-orbits. A toroidal-orbit with a capacity of $E_{-861} - E_{\pi^0}$ intersects with two r_{-137} with an inclination of 45° , corresponding to the toroidal-orbit structure of the π^0 meson. Solving this formula yields the mass of the π^0 meson.

As another case, the structural formula for the Λ particle is:

$$\frac{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 16 - \frac{E_{\Lambda}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \times 16}.$$

The initial toroidal-orbit of the Λ particle consists of 16 r_{-137} , so the left side of the formula, the molecular part, corresponds to the energy loss in the Λ particle due to shielding, while the left side of the formula represents the length of the energy gap. The formula describes a stable structure of the Λ particle, formed by a perpendicular interlocking of an r_{-861} orbit with another whose capacity is 16 times that of r_{-137} . The capacity information of the toroidal-orbits is indicated in the denominators on both sides of the formula. The length of the energy gap on the r_{-861} orbit precisely accommodates a toroidal-orbit with a capacity of $E_e \times \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 16$, signifying the tight nesting that stabilizes the Λ particle.

All mesons and baryons can be described using similar structures, and their masses calculated accordingly, as detailed in the SI. This applies equally to fundamental particles. We illustrate with the structural formula of the muons as another example:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} - \frac{E_{\mu}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} \times \sqrt{2}.$$

The formula describes the structure of the muon, which is a nested structure formed by r_{-137} and r_{-861} at a 45° angle, as shown in Figure 2. This is somewhat

similar to the toroidal-orbit structure of the π^0 meson. The matter-charge or energy on the unobstructed part of r_{-861} , not covered by r_{-137} , corresponds to the actual mass of the muon.

Figure 2: The toroidal-orbit structure of a muon.

The following describes the structural formula for the tau lepton, allowing for the calculation of the tau particle's mass using the formula below. The initial toroidal-orbit for the proton consists of two r_{-861} and one r_{-137} , which split into four identical toroidal-orbits, whereas the initial toroidal-orbit for the tau lepton consists of four r_{-861} and one r_{-137} , which split into two identical toroidal-orbits. Details are provided in the SI.

$$\frac{\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{8\pi+1}{\alpha} - \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{E_\tau}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{8\pi+1}{\alpha}\right)^2} \times \frac{4\pi+1}{16} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{8\pi+1}{\alpha}}}.$$

For particles within this mass range, their structures are very similar, hence their structural formulas are also very similar. However, for some particles with very high energies, their stability mechanisms are not based on interlocking toroidal-orbits but on other identifiable mechanisms. Below is the mass calculation formula for the Higgs particle, in fact, this is $\frac{1}{\alpha}$ times the toroidal-orbit capacity of the tau lepton:

$$E_{Higgs} = \frac{1}{\alpha} \times E_{\tau 0} \times \frac{1}{2} = \frac{8\pi+1}{\alpha^2} \times \frac{1}{2} \times E_e.$$

For the W & Z bosons, we also have certain hypotheses, such as:

$$E_W = \frac{1}{\alpha} \times (E_{-861} + E_{-137} \times 2) + E_{p0}.$$

This represents a stable toroidal-orbit structure in line with the new framework's characteristics, exhibiting energy almost identical to the measured val-

ues of the W boson, with its radius remaining unmeasurable. However, within this new framework, it simply denotes a particle with a specific energy. The same applies to the calculations for the Higgs particle; in high-energy experiments, particle reactions are indeed observed at the mass corresponding to the Higgs particle, appearing as point particles due to the unobservable radius. Yet, in the new framework, it is considered a regular particle, devoid of any specific function. Based on the simple rules in the new framework, we can identify a range of high-mass particles that are similar to them and have not yet been discovered.

It is evident that in the particle toroidal-orbit model, each particle, whether a fundamental particle or a hadron, is formed by a stable structure of toroidal-orbits, and their mass corresponds to the quantity of material-charge within the toroidal-orbits. Table 2 includes calculated mass values for several particles. For more in SI.

Table 2 | Calculated Masses and Measured Masses for Selected Particles^{7,9-13}.

Particle	Type	Calculated Value	Measured Value	Unit
$\pi^\pm$	Meson	139.574 07	139.57021(14)	MeV
π^0	Meson	134.954 62	134.9768(5)	MeV
$K^\pm$	Meson	493.713	493.677(16)	MeV
K^0	Meson	497.597	497.611(13)	MeV
$B^\pm$	Meson	5279.338 66	5279.34(12)	MeV
B^0	Meson	5279.659 88	5279.66(12)	MeV
Neutron	Baryon	939.480 35	939.56542052(54)	MeV
Λ	Baryon	1115.705 87	1115.683(6)	MeV
Muon(μ)	Lepton	106.008 08	105.6583755(23)	MeV
Tau(τ)	Lepton	1776.919	1776.91(12)	MeV
Higgs	Boson	125.385	125.25(17)	GeV
W	Boson	80 435.272	80433.5(9.4)	MeV

Quarks and Formulas for Calculating Quark Masses

In the Standard Model, quarks are considered fundamental components, whose masses, although not directly measurable due to quark confinement, can be indirectly determined through collision experiments in high-energy particle accelerators. The toroidal-orbit model suggests that all particles originate from two specific toroidal-orbits— r_{-137} and r_{-861} , with E_{-137} and E_{-861} representing their energies, respectively. By representing the capacity of a proton's toroidal-orbit as $E_{p0}/4$ and adding a few coefficients, the calculated values align closely with the measured masses of several quarks. As show in Table 3.

Table 3 |Masses of Four Quarks¹⁴⁻¹⁷.

Quark	Calculated Formula	Measured Mass	Unit
Strange (s)	$E_{-137} \times \sqrt{2} = 99.03$	$98.7_{-3.2}^{+4.0}$	MeV
Charm (c)	$E_{-861} \times 2 \times \sqrt{2} = 1244$	1246 ± 23	MeV
Top (t)	$E_{-861} \times \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 2 \times \sqrt{2} = 170.5$	172.6 ± 2.5	GeV
Bottom (b)	$\frac{E_{p0}}{4} \times 2\pi \times 2 \times \sqrt{2} = 4.221$	4.197 ± 0.008	GeV

The relationship between these calculated values and quark masses demonstrates a deep connection between the toroidal-orbit model and quark particles. In these calculations, coefficients such as α or 2π reveal a close association between different levels of toroidal-orbits, while the recurrent appearance of $\sqrt{2}$ signifies that quark masses are tightly related to the perpendicular interlocking of fundamental toroidal-orbits, suggesting quarks are not particles that can exist in reality but are energy reactions of interlocking toroidal-orbits.

The particles most closely related to up and down quarks are protons, and within the proton's structure, the toroidal-orbits intersect perpendicularly. The energy at the intersection point is given by $E_{p0} \times \frac{1}{4} - E_p \times \frac{1}{4}$. By also incorporating the coefficient $\sqrt{2}$, which represents the energy expressed at this intersection point,

we arrive at the following formula:

$$\left(E_{p0} \times \frac{1}{4} - E_p \times \frac{1}{4} \right) \times \sqrt{2} = 2.0712\text{MeV} \times 2,$$

which intriguingly mirrors the estimated mass of a pair of up quarks, with an up quark mass¹⁸ assumed to be $m_u = 2.130 \pm 0.041\text{MeV}/c^2$.

According to the Standard Model, a down quark releases an electron when it decays into an up quark. A similar expression exists in our new model, detailed in the SI. However, if we focus solely on the calculations and disregard the process, by inserting the rest energy of an electron at the intersection point of the proton's toroidal-orbits, we obtain:

$$\left(E_{p0} \times \frac{1}{4} - E_p \times \frac{1}{4} \right) \times \sqrt{2} + 1 \times E_e = 4.65538\text{MeV},$$

corresponding to the down quark value¹⁸ $m_d = 4.675 \pm 0.056\text{MeV}/c^2$.

In the new model, up and down quarks are considered to be related to the energy at the intersection when toroidal-orbits interlock, explaining their manifestation of lower mass.

In our new model, although all particles are composed of toroidal-orbits, these orbits can be classified into two types based on the motion of the matter-charges within them.

The first type is the single-rotation toroidal-orbit, where matter-charges move at the speed of light along the orbit. This type of orbit is found in leptons, such as electrons and electron neutrinos, as well as in heavier fundamental particles like the Higgs boson and W & Z bosons. The second type, the double-rotation toroidal-orbit, also features matter-charges moving at light speed, but with velocity components both along and perpendicular to the orbit. These two types of toroidal-orbits can be distinguished by measuring physical properties such as the particles' magnetic moments. Compared to the first type, the second type exhibits greater stability. Experimentally, the radius of hadrons can be measured, just for they are composed of the second type of toroidal-orbit, whereas

particles traditionally viewed as point-like without internal structure, such as electrons and Higgs bosons, consist solely of the first type.

The intersection points of the double-rotation toroidal-orbits in space exhibit enhanced stability. This phenomenon is observed in deep inelastic scattering experiments of electrons off protons: most incident electrons pass through the proton, but a very small number are repelled by “hard points” within it. These hard points are the intersection points of the proton’s toroidal-orbits, indicating that while they possess specific physical properties, they cannot exist independently as particles. This explains the essence of quark confinement; quarks, as components of the proton’s structure, cannot exist in isolation. Therefore, data related to quarks observed in high-energy experiments actually reveal the presence of vertically intersecting toroidal-orbit structures within particles. Studying quarks is essentially studying their associated toroidal-orbit structures, which led to the development of QCD in the Standard Model.

Furthermore, the Standard Model describes the interaction between quarks as the strong force, and particle decay processes as related to the weak force. In our new model, these interactions are reinterpreted: the strong force arises from interactions between double-rotation toroidal-orbits, while the weak force is associated with changes in the toroidal-orbit states. Thus, all particles, from elementary particles like electrons to composite particles like protons, are comprised of toroidal-orbits formed by matter-charges and can be studied using similar methods, focusing on the differences between the two types of toroidal-orbits rather than the traditional distinction between elementary and composite particles. For a more detailed analysis, please refer to the SI.

Some Formulas for Calculating Particle Radii

Through the structural formula of the proton, we can calculate the mass of the proton. However, as the

toroidal-orbit structure of the proton is confirmed, its circumference, width, and radius can all be directly determined by formulas. The radius of the toroidal-orbit of the matter-charge corresponding to the particle mass, namely the electromagnetic radius of the particle. This is achieved by utilizing fundamental physical constants, including the fine-structure constant α , the reduced Planck constant $\hbar$, the speed of light c , and the rest energy of the electron E_e ,

$$r_p = \frac{c\hbar}{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times \frac{1}{4} \times E_e} = 0.8308444 \times 10^{-15}\text{m},$$

where $0.831 \times 10^{-15}\text{m}$ is the proton radius measurement value reported in a 2019 study¹⁹.

We could also present more examples:

$$r_{\pi^\pm} = \frac{c\hbar}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} - \frac{E_{\pi^\pm}}{E_e}\right) \times E_e} = 0.65684 \times 10^{-15}\text{m},$$

$$r_{K^\pm} = \frac{c\hbar}{\left(\frac{E_{K^\pm}}{E_e} - \frac{2}{\alpha}\right) \times E_e} = 0.5580 \times 10^{-15}\text{m}.$$

The rest masses of particles such as the $\pi^\pm$ and $K^\pm$ mesons, denoted as $E_{\pi^\pm}$ and $E_{K^\pm}$ respectively, can be found in the Particle Data Group’s Review of Particle Physics⁷. The measured radius of $\pi^\pm$ is $r_{\pi^\pm} = 0.655(4) \times 10^{-15}\text{m}$ ⁸, the measured radius of K mesons is $0.560(31) \times 10^{-15}\text{m}$ ⁷.

The denominators of these three formulas correspond to the energy capacities of the toroidal-orbits for protons, $\pi^\pm$ mesons, and $K^\pm$ mesons. Although the details have not yet been introduced, we can already appreciate the accuracy of the calculations and their significant differences from the Standard Model. Indeed, employing the new model, the property of a particle’s radius is the easiest to calculate. However, currently, only a few particles have precise measured values for their radii available. Therefore, while the new framework can calculate the radii of more particles, there currently aren’t enough measured values to match them. However, in the future, this could serve as the most direct assessment of the new framework. For instance, while there is no measured value for the radius of the η meson yet, its radius can be calculated

based on its toroidal-orbit structure as follows:

$$r_\eta = \frac{c\hbar}{\left(\frac{E_\eta}{E_e} - \frac{2}{\alpha}\right) \times E_e} = 0.4840 \times 10^{-15} \text{m}.$$

Although the radii of electrons and muons cannot be obtained through measurement, they can similarly be calculated using the same methods, and applied in the formulas for calculating their magnetic moments, as well as serving as verification. In the SI, we describe the toroidal-orbit structures of additional particles and their respective radius formulas.

Calculated Values of Particle Magnetic Moments

Electric currents generate magnetic fields, and the rotation of matter-charges in their self-formed toroidal-orbits generates the magnetic moments of particles. As previously mentioned, once the toroidal-orbit hierarchical structure of each particle is determined, their attributes can also be identified. The magnetic moments of electrons, muons, protons, and neutrons have been precisely measured, and the comparison between calculated values obtained from the toroidal-orbit model and measured values is presented in Table 4.

Table 4 | Calculated and Measured Magnetic Moments for Four Particles^{7,20,21}.

Particle	Calculated Value	Measured Value	Unit
Electron (e)	-1.001 159 652 180 60	-1.001 159 652 180 59(13)	μ_B
Muon (μ)	-1.001 165 920 58	-1.001 165 920 61(41)	μ_B
Proton (p)	2.792 847 344 68	2.792 847 344 63(82)	μ_N
Neutron (n)	-1.913 042 72	-1.913 042 73(45)	μ_N

The focus of the calculations is to ascertain the structure within the particle's toroidal-orbits and to understand the interactions between these toroidal structures. However, the computation itself is straightforward, as exemplified by the formula for

the proton's magnetic moment:

$$\frac{\mu_p}{\mu_N} = \frac{E_p}{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times E_e} \times \sin(45^\circ) \times 4 + \left(-\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}\right) \times \frac{4\pi+1}{16} \times \sin(45^\circ) + \frac{\frac{\alpha^2}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha}}}.$$

Or the formula for the electron's magnetic moment:

$$\frac{\mu_e}{\mu_B} = (-1) + \left(-\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}\right) + \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{E_p \times \frac{1}{4}}{E_e}}} \times \sin(45^\circ) + \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{E_p \times \frac{1}{4}}{E_e}}} \times \frac{1}{(4\pi+1) \times (2\pi)} \times \frac{\alpha}{\pi}.$$

A summary of the calculation method has been briefly described in the Methods section, while more detailed calculation details and discussions can be found in the SI. It is noteworthy that the different terms in the formulas correspond to the different hierarchical levels of the particle's toroidal-orbits, and each term's specific value is related to the details within the orbit. However, whether for protons or electrons, their structures are similar, which is why these two formulas also show similar structures. It is precisely because the electron also has such a toroidal-orbit structure with a calculable radius, rather than being a point particle with no internal structure, that its magnetic moment can be succinctly calculated using this method.

In the new framework, QED within the Standard Model is reinterpreted as the interaction between charged particles and matter-charges in space, reflecting merely a difference in perspective. However, in calculating the magnetic moments of leptons, both models indeed adopt different assumptions. The new model calculates the magnetic moments of all particles using a unified method, relying on fundamental physical constants such as α , $\frac{E_p}{E_e}$, and the mathematical constant π . As long as the toroidal-orbit structure of the particles can be determined, their magnetic moments can be directly calculated. The theory's simplicity, the ease of calculations, and the accuracy of

the results are clear, though many details remain to be refined. In contrast, the Standard Model uses different theories, QED and QCD, to calculate the magnetic moments of electrons and protons, respectively, leading to a level of theoretical and computational complexity that is incomparable.

DISCUSSION

The Standard Model describes the world through a series of fundamental particles, but by depicting these particles as toroidal-orbit structures formed from even more fundamental matter, the particle toroidal-orbit model offers a deeper understanding. By directly correlating the quantity of matter-charges within the toroidal-orbits to energy, it presents a simple and easily calculable mass mechanism. The new model bridges the divide between matter, energy, and electric charge, concepts that are foundational to physics. This not only enables the calculation of particle magnetic moments and offers a direct way to re-describe electromagnetic forces (see SI), but also, undoubtedly, brings profound impacts to various aspects of physics.

Incorporating quarks into the toroidal-orbit structure, the new model shows potential for integration with the Standard Model. In fact, these two models, one focusing on detailed data analysis and the perfection of mathematical methods, and the other emphasizing intuitive understanding and the overall structure, enrich our understanding through different perspectives on the same phenomena, highlighting the importance and necessity of theoretical integration. Such an approach promises rapid developments in the field of particle physics.

In the broader field of physics, the matter-charge hypothesis and its derivative, the particle toroidal-orbit model, have led to three fundamental changes.

First, the concept of matter has been reshaped, particles are regarded as self-balancing toroidal-orbit structures formed by matter-charges, and the intro-

duction of matter-charge tightly links charge, energy, and matter itself, creating new pathways for interdisciplinary computation.

Second, our understanding of the fundamental structure of particles has been revolutionized. This debate is not just about whether particles have an internal structure but will provide a foundational explanation for relativistic effects and a new mechanism for mass generation, which will affect our understanding of the nature of space-time.

Finally, explicitly acknowledging the existence of matter-charge in the background space not only reinterprets the fundamental principles behind electromagnetic interactions and quantum phenomena but also introduces an important new research subject—the background space filled with matter-charge.

The material-charge hypothesis introduces a new perspective, prompting a reevaluation of existing physics content. The concept of material-charges in background space emerges as a vital and novel field awaiting further research. For instance, studying the density of matter-charges in space allows for the inclusion of gravity within this framework, leading to the conclusion that general relativity and gravity are similar but distinct physical phenomena with different mechanisms. From this new perspective, phenomena related to dark matter and dark energy may well receive fresh interpretations.

Compared to widely recognized theories such as the Standard Model, relativity, and quantum mechanics, the matter-charge hypothesis and the particle toroidal-orbit model are still emerging theoretical frameworks. This represents a small shift in cognitive assumptions and research perspectives. Although they show some early successes and potential, they also face many challenges. For example, the physical mechanisms underlying the toroidal-orbit width formula have not been fully revealed, and there are generally small deviations between the theoretically predicted particle masses and experimental values, indicating an inadequacy in understanding dynamical

mechanisms. We look forward to refining the the-

ory and resolving these issues through experimental progress and international cooperation.

-
- [1] M. D. Schwartz, Quantum Field Theory and the Standard Model, *Cambridge University Press*, (2014)
- [2] F. Halzen and A. D. Martin, Quarks and Leptons: An Introductory Course in Modern Particle Physics, *John Wiley & Sons*, (1984)
- [3] G. Aad et al. (ATLAS Collaboration), S. Chatrchyan et al. (CMS Collaboration), Electroweak symmetry breaking and the Higgs boson: A Review, *Annual Review of Nuclear and Particle Science*, Vol. 65:195-215 (2015)
- [4] G. Gabrielse, The Standard Model's Greatest Triumph: The Standard Model Predicts the Electron Magnetic Moment to an Astonishing Accuracy of One Part in a Trillion, *Physics Today* 66 (12), 64-65 (2013)
- [5] X. Ji, F. Yuan, Y. Zhao, What we know and what we don't know about the proton spin after 30 years, *Nat. Rev. Phys.* 3, 27-38 (2021)
- [6] L. Morel, Z. Yao, P. Cladé, S. Guellati-Khélifa, Determination of the fine-structure constant with an accuracy of 81 parts per trillion, *Nature* 588, 61-65 (2020)
- [7] E. Tiesinga, P. J. Mohr, D. B. Newell, B. N. Taylor, CODATA recommended values of the fundamental physical constants: 2018*, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* 93, 025010 (2021)
- [8] G. Colangelo, M. Hoferichter, P. Stoffer, Two-pion contribution to hadronic vacuum polarization, *JHEP* 02, 006 (2019)
- [9] M. Daum, R. Frosch, P.-R. Kettle, The charged and neutral pion masses revisited, *Phys. Lett. B* 796, 11-14 (2019)
- [10] R. L. Workman et al., Review of Particle Physics, *Progress of Theoretical and Experimental Physics*, Volume 2022, Issue 8, August 2022, 083C01 (2022)
- [11] A. M Sirunyan et al., A measurement of the Higgs boson mass in the diphoton decay channel, *Phys. Lett. B* 805, 135425 (2014)
- [12] M. Ablikim et al., Precision measurement of the mass of the τ lepton, *Phys. Rev. D* 90 (1), 012001(2014)
- [13] T. AALTONEN, et al., High-precision measurement of the W boson mass with the CDF II detector, *Sci.* 376 (6589), 170-176(2022)
- [14] C. Alexandrou et al., Quark masses using twisted-mass fermion gauge ensembles, *Phys.Rev. D*, Volume 104, Issue 7, 074515 (2021)
- [15] Y. Kiyo, G. Mishima, Y. Sumino, Determination of m_c and m_b from quarkonium 1S energy levels in perturbative QCD, *Phys.Lett.B*, Volume 752, Pages 122-127 (2016), Erratum: *Phys.Lett.B*, Volume 772, Page 878 (2017)
- [16] A. M. Sirunyan et al., Measurement of the Jet Mass Distribution and Top Quark Mass in Hadronic Decays of Boosted Top Quarks in pp Collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV, *Phys.Rev.Lett.*, Volume 124, Issue 20, 202001 (2020)
- [17] Stephan Narison, MC and MB from MBc and improved estimates of fBc and (2S)fBc(2S), *Phys.Lett.B*, Volume 802, 135221 (2020)
- [18] A. Bazavov et al., Up-, down-, strange-, charm-, and bottom-quark masses from four-flavor lattice QCD, *Phys. Rev. D* 98 (5), 054517(2018)
- [19] W. Xiong et al., A small proton charge radius from an electron-proton scattering experiment, *Nature* 575 7781, 147-150 (2019)
- [20] X. Fan, T.G. Myers, B.A.D. Sukra, G. Gabrielse, Measurement of the Electron Magnetic Moment, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 130, 071801(2023)
- [21] B. Abi et al., Measurement of the Positive Muon Anomalous Magnetic Moment to 0.46 ppm, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 126, 141801(2021)

METHODS

Conversion between Energy and Electric Charge

According to the matter-charge hypothesis, the quantity of a single type of matter-charge corresponds to electric charge, while the quantity of positive and negative matter-charges corresponds to energy. Hence, we use the symbol $|q|$ to represent the quantity of a single type of matter-charge corresponding to the electric charge q , and $|E|$ to describe the quantity of positive and negative matter-charges corresponding to the energy E . We find that the quantity of matter-charges in the rest energy of an electron, E_e , and the unit charge, e , are identical, leading to the equation:

$$|E_e| = |e|.$$

This equation serves as the foundation for calculations that bridge electric charge and energy. Fur-

thermore, if we express all three matter-charges associated with an electron in terms of electric charge—specifically, the positive and negative matter-charges derived from the rest energy, along with the electron’s inherent unit negative charge—they are equivalent to the unit charge e , though they differ in sign.

Given that a particle’s rest energy is directly proportional to the quantity of matter-charges, we obtain:

$$q = \frac{E}{E_e} \times e = X \times e.$$

If a particle’s rest energy is E , then X is the multiple of its rest energy to that of an electron. Taking a proton as an example, $X = E_p/E_e = 1836.15$, meaning $q_p = 1836.15 \times e$. This implies that the matter-charges within a proton can be divided into three parts: one corresponding to 1836.15 units of positive electric charge (positive matter-charges), the same quantity of negative matter-charges, and another corresponding to a single unit of positive electric charge. Within the proton’s own toroidal-orbit hierarchical structure, these three components rotate in toroidal-orbits of different radii. Through this formula, we convert a particle’s rest energy into electric charges rotating within different toroidal-orbits, laying the groundwork for calculating the particle’s magnetic moment.

Radius of the Outermost Toroidal-Orbit

The frequency of a photon is related to its energy, as expressed by $E = h\nu$. Considering the constant speed of light, c , we derive the formula for a photon’s wavelength: $\lambda = hc/E$. Similarly, for a toroidal-orbit carrying energy E , its circumference formula is also

$$C = \frac{hc}{E},$$

leading to the toroidal-orbit radius formula:

$$r = \frac{C}{2\pi} = \frac{c\hbar}{E}.$$

As previously mentioned, the formula for the circumference can be used to calculate the length of the

energy gap, the formula for the radius is the electromagnetic radius of the particle. Practical evidence has proven the effectiveness of these two formulas. For detailed derivations, please refer to the SI regarding photons.

Just as the unit charge e is the fundamental unit of electric charge, in the new model, the rest energy of an electron, E_e , serves as the basic unit of energy, while the electron’s toroidal-orbit, r_e , forms the foundation for all toroidal-orbits. Unlike the proton, whose matter-charges are split into interlocking toroidal-orbits, the electron has a unique characteristic—its outermost toroidal-orbit has an energy capacity of E_e , with a circumference of $C_e = 2.4263 \times 10^{-12}\text{m}$ and a radius of $r_e = 3.8615 \times 10^{-13}\text{m}$, both constants commonly used in calculations involving toroidal-orbits.

Taking the proton as an example again. The total energy capacity of the proton’s initial toroidal-orbit is $E_{p0} = E_{-861} \times 2 + E_{-137} = E_e \times (4\pi + 1) / \alpha = E_e \times 1859.08$. Dividing this into four toroidal-orbits, the energy capacity of each becomes $E_{p0}/4 = E_e \times 464.77$. Since the energy capacity of a toroidal-orbit is inversely proportional to its radius, the proton’s radius can be directly calculated as: $r_p = 3.8615 \times 10^{-13} / 464.77 = 0.83084 \times 10^{-15}\text{m}$.

Formula for Toroidal-Orbit Width and Its Application

In addition to the circumference and radius of a toroidal-orbit, when the energy capacity of the toroidal-orbit is determined, its width can also be calculated. Generally, the formula for this is:

$$W = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{X}} \times C_e.$$

Here, the square root of X represents the multiple of the toroidal-orbit’s energy capacity to E_e . From the previous discussion, the energy capacity of each of the proton’s toroidal-orbits is $E_{p0}/4 = E_e \times 464.77$, leading to its toroidal-orbit width being: $0.00002694 \times C_e$.

Considering the proton's toroidal-orbit circumference $C_p = C_e/464.77$, its energy capacity $E_{p0}/4 = E_e \times 464.77$, and the energy loss on each toroidal-orbit $E_{loss} = E_{p0}/4 - E_p/4$, we can calculate the length of the energy gap on each toroidal-orbit: $L = 0.00002654 \times C_e$. The difference between the toroidal-orbit width and the gap length is $0.0000004 \times C_e$, or $9.7 \times 10^{-19}\text{m}$. This is sufficient to illustrate that the proton's two sets of toroidal-orbits can form a vertically nested tight structure. The stability of most particles is determined by this mechanism.

Toroidal-Orbit Hierarchy

The three matter-charges composing an electron have different toroidal-orbit radii. r_e refers to the orbit of the split negative matter-charge from the rest energy, with the split positive matter-charge's toroidal-orbit located inside it, having a radius of r_e times $\alpha/2\pi = 1/861$, which is the toroidal-orbit r_{-861} . It's important to note the multiplicative relationship between their radii; if the matter-charges corresponding to a particle's rest energy are split into different hierarchical toroidal-orbits, the coefficient $\alpha/2\pi$ is the most common ratio between the radii of these two toroidal-orbits.

As for the negative matter-charges corresponding to the electron's unit negative charge, they are not points either but also have a toroidal-orbit structure. The formula for the radius of such toroidal-orbits is:

$$r_{unit\ charge} = \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{X}} \times r_e.$$

For electrons, the X to be substituted in the formula is the multiple of the actual energy within one of the proton's toroidal-orbits to the electron's rest energy, with a value of $E_p/4/E_e = 459.04$, yielding $r_{unit\ charge}$ as a toroidal-orbit with a minuscule radius. For different particles, X takes different values, but all are related to the particle's own toroidal-orbit structure. It should be noted that electrons, being leptons that do not participate in strong interactions, if cal-

culating the radius of the unit charge portion within hadrons, an additional coefficient of $1/(2\pi)$ should be included, which also reflects the second type of rotation in the hadron toroidal-orbits

Calculation of the Electron's Magnetic Moment

When a charge moves in an orbit, it generates a magnetic moment. In classical electromagnetism, the formula for orbital magnetic moment is:

$$m = I \times S = \left(q \times \frac{v}{2\pi r}\right) \times (\pi r^2) = \frac{1}{2}qvr.$$

Calculating the orbital magnetic moment produced by the electron's outermost toroidal-orbit, by substituting the unit negative charge e (derived from the rest energy of the electron), the speed of light c , into the radius of the electron's outermost toroidal-orbit r_e , we obtain:

$$m = \frac{1}{2} \times e \times c \times r_e = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{e}{m_e} \times \hbar = 1\mu_B.$$

μ_B is the Bohr magneton, which is also the unit of expression for the electron's magnetic moment. Since all three matter-charges of the electron correspond to the unit charge, with their rotational speed being the speed of light c , and the radii of these three toroidal-orbits have already been calculated, the orbital magnetic moment generated by each of these charges can be calculated. After considering the type, rotational direction, and spatial structure of the matter-charges within each layer of toroidal-orbits (the outer two layers are horizontal, but the toroidal-orbit containing the electron's unit charge is inclined at 45° to the horizontal plane), the formula for the electron's magnetic moment is derived as:

$$\frac{\mu_e}{\mu_B} = (-1) + \left(-\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}\right) + \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{E_p \times \frac{1}{4}}{E_e}}} \times \sin(45^\circ).$$

Herein, μ_e is $-1.00115965224833\mu_B$, which aligns well with the latest empirical measurement of $-1.00115965218059(13)\mu_B$.

Calculation of the Muon's Magnetic Moment

Since the number of matter-charges within a toroidal-orbit are directly proportional to the electric charge and inversely proportional to the radius, for an ideal toroidal-orbit, regardless of the corresponding energy amount, as long as a single type of matter-charge rotates along its own created toroidal-orbit at the speed of light, the magnetic moment it contributes should be $1\mu_B$.

Here, we consider the muon as an example, with a more comprehensive explanation provided in SI. Similarly to the electron, the muon is divided into three matter-charges, occupying different toroidal-orbits from those of the electron. However, because of the aforementioned relationship, the negative and positive matter-charges corresponding to the muon's rest energy, occupying their respective toroidal-orbits, ultimately contribute a magnetic moment same to that of the electron, which is $(1) + (\frac{\alpha}{2\pi})$. Then, specifically calculating the radius of the toroidal-orbit for the muon's unit charge and substituting $X = 1/\alpha$ into the formula for $r_{unit\ charge}$, we determine the toroidal-orbit of this portion of matter-charge. Proceeding to calculate its orbital magnetic moment, we derive the formula for the muon's magnetic moment:

$$\frac{\mu_\mu}{\mu_B} = (-1) + \left(-\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}\right) + \left(-\frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}}\right) = -1.00116595870,$$

while the most recent empirical measurement is $-1.00116592061(41)\mu_B$.

Calculation of the Proton's and Neutron's Magnetic Moments

Electrons and muons, being leptons, have their magnetic moments measured in Bohr magnetons. However, for hadrons like protons and neutrons, which participate in the strong interaction, although the matter-charges within their constitutive toroidal-orbits still move at the speed of light, their velocity

in the primary direction of the toroidal-orbit is only $c \times E_e/E_p = c/1836.15$, and in the direction perpendicular to the toroidal-orbit, they rotate at a faster velocity— $c \times \sqrt{1 - (E_e/E_p)^2}$. The rotation in the perpendicular direction also generates a magnetic moment, but it is canceled out by the magnetic moment generated on the opposite side of the toroidal-orbit. However, due to the reduced rotation speed of the matter-charges in the toroidal-orbit's main direction, these toroidal-orbits with a dual rotation characteristic, their unit of magnetic moment is not the Bohr magneton, but the nuclear magneton μ_N , corresponding to $1/1836.15$ of a Bohr magneton.

To illustrate the calculation process of the proton's magnetic moment, first consider the proton's four outermost toroidal-orbits that are perpendicular to each other. Based on their spatial structure, they should contribute a magnetic moment of $\sin(45^\circ) \times 4 = 2.82842712\mu_N$. However, taking into account the energy gap on the proton's toroidal-orbits, their contributed magnetic moment changes to $E_p/E_{p0} \times \sin(45^\circ) \times 4 = 2.79354377\mu_N$, which is very close to the measured magnetic moment of the proton, $2.79284734463(82)\mu_N$. Further considering the other two parts of matter-charges located in toroidal-orbits, we obtain the formula for the proton's magnetic moment in main text, as introduced earlier in the main text.

Following the same logic and applying the formula, considering specific details in the neutron structure, as well as its unique situation of containing both a unit positive charge and a unit negative charge, we derive the formula for the neutron's magnetic moment:

$$\frac{\mu_n}{\mu_N} = \left(-\sqrt{2} - \frac{1}{2}\right) + \frac{\alpha}{2\pi} + \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{2\pi} + \left(\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}\right)^2 \times \sin(45^\circ)\right).$$

As shown in Table 4, the calculated values for the magnetic moments of the proton and neutron are almost identical to the measured values.

Advances and Challenges

We have presented several formulae related to toroidal-orbits, it must be noted that the formula for the width of a toroidal-orbit and the formula for the radius of the unit charge portion remain empirical. We have yet to elucidate the physical mechanisms behind them. However, the validity of the toroidal-orbit width formula has been confirmed through examination of a sufficient number of particles. As for the radius formula of the unit charge portion, although currently applied to only four particles with sufficiently accurate magnetic moment measurements, its provision of extremely high precision leads us to believe in its validity, pending further understanding.

The calculated values for the magnetic moments of protons and neutrons are exceedingly close to their measured values, and given the current measurement precision, we do not need to provide a fourth term for their magnetic moment formulae. However, the calculated values for the magnetic moments of electrons and muons, though trending consistently, still present discrepancies when compared to their measured values. Nevertheless, adding a correction term to each of the formulae for the electron and muon magnetic moments, changing them to:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mu_e}{\mu_B} &= (-1) + \left(-\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}\right) + \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{E_p \times \frac{1}{4}}{E_e}}} \times \sin(45^\circ) \\ &+ \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{E_p \times \frac{1}{4}}{E_e}}} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{\pi}}{(4\pi + 1) \times (2\pi)} = -1.00115965218060, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mu_\mu}{\mu_B} &= (-1) + \left(-\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}\right) + \left(-\frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}}\right) \\ &+ \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} \times \frac{\sin(45^\circ) + \alpha}{(4\pi + 1) \times (2\pi)} = -1.00116592058, \end{aligned}$$

yields numbers almost identical to the measured values, as shown in Table 4.

Summary and Future Research Directions

Among the several fundamental properties of particles, determining the radius is relatively straightforward, requiring only the determination of the capacity of a particle's toroidal-orbit. Determining the mass of particles is also not difficult, although some minor discrepancies always exist. However, based on the numerous structural and mass formulae provided in the SI for a wide range of particles, we can be confident that the general direction we have proposed is reliable. Nonetheless, when it comes to pinpointing the precise magnetic moments of particles, we acknowledge that there remains a significant lack of understanding regarding the nature of matter-charges.

The structure of a particle's outermost toroidal-orbits can be easily determined, making the rough calculation of a particle's magnetic moment straightforward. However, the formation mechanisms of inner toroidal-orbits are not fully understood and lack any direct means of observation. Therefore, while indeed we have identified consistent patterns in the inner toroidal-orbits of electrons, muons, protons, and neutrons—allowing us to formulate precise calculations of their magnetic moments—for other particles, especially hyperons, we have yet to find a lead, preventing us from providing accurate predictions of their fine magnetic moments. Furthermore, although the introduction of correction terms in the magnetic moment formulae for electrons and muons enables a perfect match between calculated and measured values, and the mathematical structure of these correction terms allows us to speculate on their physical significance—seemingly reflecting interactions between different levels of toroidal-orbits—currently, there is a lack of sufficient data to validate these hypotheses. Moreover, as measurement technologies advance, existing values for particle properties may be adjusted, and many of the magnetic moment measurements for hyperons, dating back decades, cannot serve as a reliable basis for inferring the laws of interaction between matter-charges.

Therefore, although the matter-charge hypothesis and the particle toroidal-orbit model provide an innovative and comprehensive framework, achieving a perfect resolution to all related questions and a comprehensive explanation of the dynamics of matter-charges still requires ongoing scientific exploration and collaborative research.

Data availability All data utilized in this study directly derive from publicly published literature, with specific sources of data and analyses clearly indicated in the references. Access to each item of data can be achieved through the DOI links provided in the corresponding references.

Competing interests The authors declare no competing interests.

Supplementary Information is available for this paper.